

MACHINES FOR TILLAGE BETWEEN ROWS OF VINEYARDS WITHOUT TIPPING AND FORMING IRRIGATION DITCHES

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Аннотация. Рациональная обработка почвы-непрерывное условие повышения урожайности винограда и улучшения его качества. Очень важно правильно установить глубину вспашки, которая зависит от типа почвы, ее увлажненности и применяемой агротехники. Полоса ограничена по бокам двумя валиками высотой 16-18 сантиметров. Впитывание воды происходит при движении ее тонким слоем по всей поверхности полосы. На полосу воду выпускают из временного оросителя или из выводной борозды при помощи прорезов в валиках или жестяных сифонов. Задача поливальщиков при таком способе полива состоит в том, чтобы сплошь покрыть полосу тонким слоем движущейся воды. В этом случае следует устраивать земляные валики поперек уклона с таким расчетом, чтобы они временно задерживали воду или изменяли ее направление до подхода общего потока.

Ключевые слова: зима, весна, машины, почва, метров, долбление, виноградники, культивации, орошение

Abstract. Rational tillage is an indispensable condition for increasing the yield of grapes and improving its quality. It is very important to correctly set the depth of plowing, which depends on the type of soil, its moisture content and the agricultural technology used. The strip is limited on the sides by two rollers 16-18 centimeters high. Water absorption occurs when it moves in a thin layer over the entire surface of the strip. Water is released onto the strip from a temporary sprinkler or from a lead-out furrow using slots in rollers or tin siphons. The task of waterers with this method of irrigation is to completely cover the strip with a thin layer of moving water. In this case, earthen rollers should be arranged across the slope so that they temporarily retain water or change its direction until the general flow approaches.

Key words: winter, spring, machines, soil, meters, chiselling, vineyards, cultivation, irrigation

Rational tillage is an indispensable condition for increasing the yield of grapes and improving its quality. It includes a system of techniques for influencing the soil, ensuring the creation of the most favorable conditions for plant growth in specific

natural, organizational and economic conditions. The system of soil maintenance in vineyards should provide for the greatest accumulation and conservation of moisture in it, the creation of an optimal air regime, a constant increase in soil fertility, protection from water and wind erosion, the destruction of weeds and pests of the vine, the incorporation of organic and mineral fertilizers, covering the bushes for the winter and opening them in the spring with a covering culture.

Too wet soil sticks to the working bodies of tillage machines, the quality of covering and the productivity of the units are reduced. It is very important to correctly set the depth of plowing, which depends on the type of soil, its moisture content and the agricultural technology used. In the Sea, autumn plowing on cohesive soils is carried out by 22-25 cm. In cases where the root system of the grapes is located close to the soil surface or it is not advisable to turn its deep layers up, they plow smaller.

After covering the bushes, row spacing should not be harrowed. The wavy surface of the vineyard absorbs autumn and winter precipitation better and resists water and wind erosion. The grapes are usually spudded in such a way that the head and sleeves of the bushes are covered, as well as 4-5 eyes from the base of annual shoots. At the same time, the earth from the row spacing must be taken evenly, and even better, at some distance from the head of the bush (50-60 cm) in order to avoid exposing the root system. Spring processing begins with the opening of the bushes. They start it as soon as the condition of the soil allows, which usually falls on the second or third decade of March, and in years with a long spring - at the beginning of April. Open the bushes in two stages. When using it, it is necessary to ensure that the opening bodies are buried in the soil by no more than 10-15 cm, and the disks have an angle of inclination forward and towards the shaft. It is advisable to combine the preliminary plowing of the covering shafts with the harrowing of the soil in one track, using two "zigzag" harrow links for this. To improve soil aeration and weed control, chiselling is carried out with narrow-loosening paws to a depth of 20-25 cm, depending on the type of soil and the location of the root system of the bushes. By the time the buds open, spring work in the vineyard should be completed. In summer, row-spacing cultivation is carried out with simultaneous tillage in rows. This is necessary for weed control, accumulation and conservation of moisture. The amount of cultivation depends on meteorological conditions, the degree of development of weeds and soil type. In arid conditions of the Azov region, 4-5 cultivations are usually enough. The last time the soil is cultivated at the beginning of the ripening of the grapes.

In the struggle for more complete moisture retention and energy savings, one should strive to reduce the number of treatments. Frequent loosening without regard to the state of the soil also leads to the destruction of its structure. On sandy and

shell-sandy soils, excessive loosening often causes it to be blown out, as a result, the root system of bushes is exposed, shoots, leaves and clusters are spotted with sand.

If, for some reason, the soil was blown out in the vineyard and the roots were exposed, special techniques are used - sediment and backfilling. To carry out the draft of the bush, carefully dig a hole on the side to expose the roots as much as possible. After that, the bush is lowered down, the roots are covered with sand, and covered with straw or reeds from above. Bedding is done in autumn or even winter. For this purpose, deep plowing of row-spacings is carried out and a layer of sand of 30-35 cm is added to the bushes. These techniques contribute to the rapid recovery of grape bushes. To avoid the formation of a compacted soil layer ("soles"), the first cultivation is carried out 12-15 cm, and the subsequent ones are 1-2 cm smaller. Inter-row cultivation with tillage in rows is carried out by PRVN-2.5A or PRVM-3 machines equipped with PRVN-72000 and PRVM-11000 devices, respectively, but they can only be used on fruit-bearing vineyards, that is, not younger than three years. This is due to the fact that young plantations that do not have thickened perennial wood are easily cut at the base of the bush with knives of devices. For the same reason, in a vineyard where plantings have been repaired by replanting chibouks, seedlings or layering, wooden or metal pegs must be installed near each young plant. This machine is designed to work in row spacings of 2 and 2.5 meters in combination with a KD-35 tractor. All types of work are carried out by various working bodies that can be replaced. The permanent part of the machine is a trolley, consisting of a frame with a trailer, an axle with wheels and an automatic machine with a depth adjustment mechanism.

Two hanging frames are included for attaching the working bodies to the machine. One of them is used to work in the row spacing with a width of 2 meters, and the second, large, in the row spacing of 2.5 meters.

Recently, the machine has been additionally equipped with special devices that make it possible to: cut irrigation furrows in irrigated vineyards, planting furrows in a grape nursery and sow fertilizers when renovating the plantation.

Following the pavers, a tractor with a covering plow passes and closes the bushes.

It should be noted that usually the land for digging: the vines are taken from one side of the row, as a result of which a strip of recesses is formed in the aisle on the side. If the wheel falls into these recesses, then the car gets a side roll. The working bodies located to this side go deeper than the others and, due to the asymmetry of the load, the machine blows in the direction of less resistance. At the same time, the stability of the machine is disturbed, and the quality of the covering is sharply reduced. Therefore, the land for digging the vines must be taken either directly from

the bushes or in the middle of the aisle, but not where the wheels of the covering plow should pass.

Spring loosening is an important agricultural technique aimed at restoring the loose structure of the soil compacted during spring work in vineyards, retaining moisture in it, and facilitating the development of the root system.

The depth of processing in the spring loosening is recommended to be brought up to 20-25 centimeters.

If loosening to a depth of more than 20 centimeters is necessary, then the paws should be spaced less often: for row spacing of 2.5 meters - seven pieces, and for row spacing of 2 meters - five.

Rice. 1. Scheme of arrangement of paws of a chisel cultivator for work in row spacing of 2.5 meters

After the passage of the chisel cultivator, the surface remains ridged. Therefore, it is necessary to attach a heavy chain (loop) or a harrow hitch to the chisel for leveling. The performance of the unit in this work reaches at different lengths of ruts from 3.5 to 4.5 hectares per shift. Tractor caterpillars compact the soil especially strongly as a result of its repeated passage along the same track between rows. Compaction along the tractor track is distributed up to 20 and even 40 centimeters deep and worsens the physical properties of the soil. Deep loosening of the soil with a chisel cultivator, destroying the track, significantly reduces its harmful effect. The complete destruction of the track is achievable only by updating the plantage. The greatest value of spring chiselling lies in the fact that a loose layer up to 26-28 centimeters thick created by the cultivator well protects the soil during spring and summer from moisture loss and contributes to normal air exchange. The normal time for spring chiseling is the middle or second half of April, that is, after the garter of bushes. Chiselling should not be delayed in order to avoid large losses of soil

moisture. Therefore, you should hurry with spring work in the vineyards: repairing the trellis, dry pruning of bushes, tying up the vines.

It must be remembered that correctly and timely carried out spring loosening significantly improves environmental conditions, minimizes the number of summer cultivations. Soil care during spring and summer consists of cultivation, the purpose of which is to control weeds and break up the crust that forms on the surface of the soil after rains. This work, depending on the conditions and possibilities of the economy, is carried out in different ways. In vineyards planted in a trellis-row way, with fairly wide aisles, it is performed by tractor or horse-drawn cultivators (horse-mounted ones are preferable). In the vineyards, cultivated with the help of manual labor, hoeing is carried out.

During the season, taking into account the meteorological conditions, from 3 to 5 cultivations are carried out. The latter is usually timed to coincide with the beginning of the ripening of early grape varieties. In mechanized vineyards, where chiselling is applied in the spring, usually no more than 2-3 cultivations are required. The depth of cultivation is from 6 to 12 centimeters: the first one is on b-8, and each subsequent one is 2 centimeters deeper.

Before each cultivation, manual hoeing is necessarily carried out in rows between bushes to a depth of 6 to 10 centimeters.

Periodic renewal (deep loosening) to a large extent returns the loose structure to the soil, promotes the growth of the root system in the loosening zone and enhances the fruiting of bushes.

Rice. 2. Scheme of arrangement of weeding paws of a chisel cultivator for work in row spacing of 2.5 meters

Bushes respond to this event with a significant increase in yield (by 20-30 percent), especially in the second year after the renewal of the plantation, of course, provided that this operation is carried out correctly and in a timely manner. Similarly, it has been found that deep loosening of the soil in each row spacing, and not through

one, as previously recommended, gives the best results. The performance of the unit at this job is 3.75-4.75 hectares per shift.

In the year of renewal of the plantation, it is quite possible to do without autumn chiselling.

It is highly desirable that the soil is less compacted between cultivations. To do this, if possible, they should be timed to coincide with the completion of the next work on caring for the vineyards: tying the vines, breaking off the shoots, chasing, etc. The initial loose structure of the soil in the vineyards, created by plantation plowing, is lost over time as a result of natural settlement, under the influence of multiple passes of tractors, implements, trampling by people. The soil becomes more and more compacted over the years-the plantation "gets old". Accordingly, the conditions of aeration, soil moisture and plant nutrition worsen. All this negatively affects the growth and fruiting of the bushes.

Rice. Fig. 3. The profile of the soil surface and the loosening zone during the autumn renewal of the plantation with a three-line tiller

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In the year of renewal of the plantation, it is quite possible to do without autumn chiselling. Most vineyards practice plantage renewal every 5 years. However, the latest experiments of the institute of viticulture have established that in areas with a fairly deep planting of grape bushes (at least 40-50 centimeters), the best results are obtained with a more frequent renewal of the planting - once every three years.

Plantage renewal should be carried out primarily in old vineyards, as well as in areas where there was no continuous, deep plantation plowing of the soil before planting grapes.

The cutting of irrigation furrows is usually combined with regular cultivation. Autumn chiselling is also combined with the cutting of irrigation furrows for winter water-recharging irrigation.

Additional loosening of the soil after irrigation on irrigated vineyards is recommended to be carried out in 2 steps: on the 2nd-3rd day after irrigation - light horse loosening (harrowing) to cover moisture and seal irrigation furrows, and on the 8th-9th day - chiselling to a depth of 15 -18 centimeters (to prevent the drying of the soil and the formation of lumps).

In irrigated vineyards, planting is renewed every 3 years.

Finally, it should be taken into account that the best results when fertilizing vineyards in the conditions of the Rostov and Kamensk regions are obtained by combining the usual surface application over the entire area with local deep application (directly into the zone of distribution of the main mass of roots) and top dressing.

Fertilizers applied according to such a system not only enrich the upper horizon, but also the deeper, moister layers of the soil, where the bulk of small suction roots are widespread and where fertilizers are quickly absorbed by plants.

This provides a more complete and timely supply of plants with the necessary nutrients, improves the water-air regime of the soil, increases the biochemical activity and vital activity of the vine root system in it. As a result, all this significantly increases the yield of vine plantations.

Rational irrigation in combination with all other methods of advanced agricultural viticulture creates great opportunities for obtaining high sustainable grape yields. This applies to all areas of the Rostov and Kamensk regions, but primarily to the eastern and southeastern regions, which are part of the arid climate zone.

The success of irrigation largely depends on the correct application of the timing, norms and methods of irrigation that most fully meet the requirements of the vine. You can start moisture charging after the grape harvest, from about September 25, and continue until the onset of frost, until about November 20. Since it is impossible to cover the vineyards for the winter with too damp earth, the moisture-charging irrigation should be stopped 6-10 days before the vineyards are covered.

The first is after the flowering of grapes (the second half of June and the beginning of July), the second - before the ripening of the berries (the second half of July and the beginning of August). In the western regions, one vegetation watering can be given during the period of berry growth (approximately from June 20 to July

10), but in particularly dry years, it is advisable to increase the number of vegetation irrigations to two.

It is very important to correctly calculate the irrigation rate. So it is customary to call the amount of water in cubic meters, which is consumed per hectare, for one irrigation. The irrigation norm is the sum of all irrigation norms for the growing season.

To calculate the irrigation rate, it is necessary to have data on the field moisture capacity of the soil, the thickness of the active moistened layer, the actual soil moisture before irrigation, the height of the specified moisture level (as a percentage of the field moisture capacity).

To maintain soil moisture at this level in the conditions of the Rostov and Kamensk regions, 2-3 vegetation irrigations and one sub-winter watering are required.

In the current year's planting vineyard, the first watering with a norm of 400-500 cubic meters is carried out when seedlings are planted in a permanent place, the second watering - approximately in the first half of June, the third - in the first half of July, and sometimes the fourth - in early August. For all four, the irrigation rate is 500-600 cubic meters.

In the vineyard of the second year of planting, the first vegetation irrigation is given in June, the second in July, with irrigation rates of 600-700 cubic meters. Podzimny moisture-charging watering on young vineyards is carried out at the same time as for fruit-bearing plantations, with a rate of approximately 1000-1200 cubic meters.

Vegetative irrigation in young vineyards is best done along furrows cut at a distance of about 40 centimeters on each side of a row of grape bushes. Water is passed through the furrows until the soil is moistened to a depth of at least a meter. Moisture-charging irrigation (after sheltering the bushes for the winter) can be carried out along narrow strips, for which the covering shafts will serve as side rollers.

Watering and loosening the soil are closely related. Untimely loosening of the soil after watering nullifies its effectiveness. Therefore, after each watering, as soon as the soil begins to dry out slightly, it must be loosened to a depth of 16-18 centimeters.

Soil moisture in all cases is determined in the usual way: soil samples taken by a drill from different depths are weighed, then dried in an oven at a temperature of 102-105 degrees for 6-7 hours and weighed again. Drying of the soil continues to a constant weight. The percentage of moisture is calculated by the formula:

To find out what is the limiting field moisture capacity of the soil, at least two sites measuring a meter per meter are allocated at typical sites of the site. A box of

the same size without a bottom is placed on each of them, the height of the walls of which is 30-40 centimeters.

After about two days, soil moisture is determined at each site. Soil samples are taken every 20-25 centimeters to a depth of at least 1.5 meters in three repetitions. The average humidity in a 1.5-meter soil layer on irrigated areas will be the maximum field moisture capacity.

The volumetric weight of the soil is the ratio of the weight of any volume of soil in its natural composition to the weight of the same volume of water. Find out the volumetric weight of the soil like this. A sample of soil of a certain volume with an undisturbed structure is taken, weighed and dried in the same way as when determining soil moisture. Volumetric weight is calculated using the formula:

In practice, such methods of watering vineyards are known: along flowing furrows; along flooded blunt furrows; along the stripes.

Choose the method of irrigation depending on the soil, topography and slope of the area.

Furrow irrigation is applicable in areas with a slope ranging from 0.02 to 0.002.

With this method of irrigation, water is absorbed into the soil while moving in a thin stream along the bottom of the furrow. The dimensions of the cross-section of the furrows must ensure the passage of the jet (according to the slope) from 0.2 to 1 liter per second.

On large slopes, the jet force must be limited to sizes at which the speed of water movement along the furrow does not lead to soil erosion. On small slopes, the force of the jet must match the throughput of the furrows and ensure high productivity of the irrigators.

Rice. 4. Completion of the VUM-60 machine for cutting slit-like furrows

If the vineyard is located on a site with a significant slope in the direction of the rows (0.02-0.01), then the irrigation jet can be applied at a rate of 0.2-0.5 liters per

second. To pass such a jet, the depth of the furrows should be from 12 to 18 centimeters. The length of the furrows depends on the magnitude of the slope and the nature of the soil. The greater the row spacing and the less

On terrain with a smaller slope (0.009-0.002), an irrigation jet is usually used from 0.5 to 1 or more liters per second. To pass such a jet, deeper furrows are required, the cutting of which is provided by plow working bodies (Fig. 5).

Rice. 5. Completion of the VUM-60 machine for cutting two deep irrigation furrows

On flooded blunt furrows, it is possible to irrigate areas with a slight, that is, less than 0.002, slope. Here, soil moisture occurs due to the water filling the furrow, so a large water supply is needed. The task of the irrigator is to fill the furrows as soon as possible. Blunt furrows should be deep (that is, capacious enough) and pass a jet - 3-5 or more liters per second. Vineyards with a well-leveled surface and a slight one-sided slope along the rows (0.002-0.004) are watered along the strips, which is relatively rare in practice. The strip is limited on the sides by two rollers 16-18 centimeters high. Water absorption occurs when it moves in a thin layer over the entire surface of the strip. The water supply with this irrigation method can be 4-6 liters per meter of strip width.

Water is released onto the strip from a temporary sprinkler or from a lead-out furrow using slots in rollers or tin siphons. The task of waterers with this method of irrigation is to completely cover the strip with a thin layer of moving water. During

irrigation, water should not be allowed to go far ahead in separate streams or accumulate for a long time in depressions. In this case, earthen ridges should be arranged across the slope in such a way that they temporarily retain water or change its direction until the general flow approaches.

The time to stop watering in strips is also important for uniform wetting of the bottom of the strip. With a specific jet of 4-5 liters per second, the water supply should be stopped as soon as the total area of the strip is filled by 95 percent.

The strips are cut with a VUM-60 machine. When cutting several furrows in one pass, it is very important to place them in the row spacing so that:

Rice. Fig. 6. Schemes of placement of furrows, cut by the VUM-60 machine, in various configurations: 1 - with a chisel cultivator; 2 - deep loosener; 3 - a plow with one-sided dumping bodies; 4 - a plow with a double-dump body

The soil discarded by the furrow dumps did not fall within the protective zone of the rows, from where it cannot be taken during post-irrigation cultivation;

The tracks of a tractor used in post-irrigation would be located on inter-furrow elevations, and not on marshy furrows. The layouts of the furrows cut by the VUM-60 machine are shown in fig. 6. It is necessary to cut the irrigation network from 2 to 4 times during the season. This work is carried out independently or combined with one of the next tillage operations. Cutting the irrigation network for early water-recharging irrigation can be combined with post-harvest chiseling or planting renewal, and for late - with covering grapes. Cutting the irrigation network for vegetative irrigation and closing it after each irrigation coincides in terms with the summer cultivation.

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